

TITLE

REVITALIZATION: INDIA'S RESPONSIBLE PUSH FOR ATMANIRBHARTA

Ms. Nalini Shanker, Birla Institute of Management Technology, Greater Noida

Ms. Shambhavi Agarwal, Khandelwal College of Management & Technology, Bareilly

ABSTRACT

2020 was a year full of ups and downs, Covid19 and many brand-new experiences were there to have. It didn't matter if it was a medical industry or a small business; everyone was directly impacted. It was a difficult period for the whole country as well as for us. On 12th May 2022, the Indian Prime Minister flagged off Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan with a new version and vision of “Make in India”. With the goal of reducing India's reliance on foreign nations for goods, commodities, technology, and sustenance as well as rebuilding the COVID-19-devastated economy, the Government of India announced The Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan or Self-Reliant India Mission. The idea of self-reliance is neither novel nor contentious – it arguably traces its historicity to the latter years of the Indian freedom movement when *swadesi* became a potent symbol of a self-reliant India. This paper aims to understand the impact and progress of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan on the IT sector of the country. This paper also focuses on identifying fields where we still lack behind and need more improvement which include Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, IoT, and others.

Keywords: *Atmanirbhar Bharat, Artificial Intelligence, Covid19, Digital India, Development, Economy, Growth, Self-reliant, Technology*

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RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To explain the unexplored horizons of Atmanirbhar Bharat.
- To examine the causal relationship between Atmanirbhar Bharat and technology.
- To analyze the interdependency of self-reliance and digital India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach used is the Qualitative method. In this approach, the research contains a complete and detailed description of the facts observed. The relevant approach to the overall research design is the challenges that Digital India is facing i.e., in the technology and demographic sectors, and how our research objectives thoroughly focused on the same. The data used for the research has been taken from validated Government published information.

Suggestive and theoretical perspectives are defined to support the explanation of observed behaviors. As descriptive research is being used, there can be certain limitations that affect the data-gathering process such as instant updates, new announcements, and news & other related aspects which have an impact on the future.

INTRODUCTION

By becoming Atmanirbhar, India plans to revive its such small industries which used to contribute in high economic growth but are not functional now as some of the countries like China have dumped their inferior products at low prices in the

Indian Market- a strategy which has made thousands of scale and cottage industries go out of track.

India has suffered a lot in this coronavirus health hazard initially as it was taken aback due to the sudden spread of China originated virus. There was a shortage of masks, gloves, sanitizers, and PPE kits for the medical professionals who are the warriors to cure the infected people.

No country could come to help in this global pandemic as all of them were suffering from a similar problem. India then stood up firmly on its feet and proved its mettle by providing medicines to the USA and other countries which were suffering from the global 19 pandemic.

In order to bridge the economic and digital divides between the haves and the have-nots, Atmanirbhar Bharat would rest on five pillars, from which a New India could pole vault to an age of sustainable economic prosperity and societal good. Strengthening these pillars through the development of an underpinning ecosystem of institutionalized skill development, cutting-edge research, and technology-driven innovations is essential if we are to make them truly powerful and resilient, built to withstand any onslaughts of possible new crises.

PILLARS OF ATMANIRBHAR BHARAT

Five pillars of Atmanirbhar Bharat were outlined- Economy (Quantum jumps, not incremental changes), Infrastructure (one that represents modern India), System (technology-driven), Demography (vibrant demography of the largest demography), and Demand (full utilization of the power of demand and supply).

To begin with the pillar of vibrant demography, India enjoys a demographic dividend, unlike any other nation in the world, with over 65% of the population under the age of 35, more than 1.4 million schools, 10,500 engineering, and related institutions, and an astounding 39,000 colleges and universities.¹ By emphasizing the development of managerial, technical, and vocational skills as well as encouraging an innovative and entrepreneurial culture at the school, university, and industry levels, we must allow the channeling of this youthful energy towards nation-building activities. Such communities can be developed and supported through the creative uses of newly emerging digital technologies. Numerous ed-tech startups now have an enormous chance to develop and use wireless, 5G communication, mobile AR/VR, and AI technologies to power the same.

Second is the pillar of infrastructure. India has over 715 districts, more than 4000 cities and 6,00,000 villages.² The nation needs smart villages and several hundred smart cities to become active hubs of livelihood enablement, innovation, and job creation. This is essential to stop our economy from growing unevenly and unsustainable urban migration to a select few tier-1 towns. The construction of digital highways, another component of the infrastructure pillar, would be necessary to guarantee that innovations in housing, healthcare, education, and employment opportunities reach every ordinary citizen. Young, creative businesspeople have a wonderful chance to take advantage of this and build expanding, influential organizations on a global scale.

¹ R. Ramanan, “Powering Aatmanirbhar Bharat through innovation and entrepreneurship”, <https://www.niti.gov.in/powering-aatmanirbhar-bharat-through-innovation-and-entrepreneurship>

² R. Ramanan, “Powering Aatmanirbhar Bharat through innovation and entrepreneurship”, <https://www.niti.gov.in/powering-aatmanirbhar-bharat-through-innovation-and-entrepreneurship>

The pillar of demand presents an unprecedented opportunity for Make in India in every industry. India has one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, over 1.3 billion people, a young population, a growing middle class, and accessible, affordable advanced technology to reimagine new solutions to both current and emerging consumer requirements. In every sector—agriculture, healthcare, education, water management, clean and renewable energy, affordable housing, defense, space, transportation, or retail—new solutions and consumer- or citizen-centric services are in high demand. This is the perfect time for thousands of startups and businesses to capitalize on this demand.

The pillar of science is up next. The impressive expansion of India's 180 billion USD, It/ITES, and biotech sectors over the past ten years has demonstrated to the rest of the world India's scientific, engineering, and technological prowess and powers. The finest multinational corporations in the world are rushing to establish sizable R&D hubs in India and utilize Indian talent. The world-class innovative talent of Aatmanirbhar Bharat is now focused internally, developing goods and services for the Indian market on a level with those of other nations. When technology is used properly, it creates a "by the people, for the people" type of system and a beneficial cascade effect, giving users the unheard-of ability to redefine and apply the rules while providing security and accountability. However, to truly make a nation self-reliant, it is critical to recognize and acknowledge its subjectivities, which in turn must dictate policymaking and governance.

Lastly, the pillar of economic growth, India needs to make sure that its rapid economic progress includes societal progress given that 22% of its population still lives in poverty, 44% of its economy is still agri-based, many districts continue to struggle with unacceptable rates of infant and maternal mortality, and only 13% of its entrepreneurs are women. Ensuring gender equality, addressing economic

inequality, and providing equal chances for communities with disabilities are important. Fast-growing economies like ours also need to be very cautious about issues linked to climate change. Sustainable Development Goals must therefore continue to be the primary goal of every organization.

In a move to measuring India's self-reliance, industry body CII (confederation of Indian Industry) and accountancy firm PwC have developed an "Atmanirbhar Index" (AI). The index is expressed as the ratio of the country's total exports and imports. The index classifies India into 20 sectors including textiles, aluminum, electronics, food products, and transport, etc. The government announced a total of 3 Atmanirbhar packages worth Rs.29.87 trillion (USD 370 billion) in relation to the covid19 pandemic in India.

ATMANIRBHAR INDEX

In FY 2022, the index had a reading of 0.69 with an export value of \$ 422 billion and an import value of \$613 billion. An index value greater than 1 for a sector means India is Atmanirbhar in that sector. While a value less than 1 means that India is not self-reliant in that sector.

AI>1 = Atmanirbhar

AI<1 = Not Atmanirbhar

As per the report in FY 2022, 8 out of the 20 sectors had an index reading of greater than 1. Trade surplus has increased for 6 of these in the last five years. Among the sectors with AI, less than 1 or contraction has been seen in the import share of electronics, diamond, machinery, minerals, wood products and vegetable products. India's export exhibited a positive growth of 10.79% over the period last year.

TRADE DURING NOVEMBER 2022-

		November 2022 (USD billion)	November 2021 (USD billion)
Merchandise	Exports	31.99	31.80
	Imports	55.88	53.03
Services	Exports	26.23	20.67
	Imports	13.44	12.63
Overall trade	Exports	58.22	52.46
(merchandise + services)	Imports	69.33	65.65
	Trade Balance	-11.11	-13.19

The main thing to notice is that in FY2022, the exports and imports of India get improved. The imports got increased by 5 % and exports by 10% approximately. Thus, we can say that India is improving its exports which will result in a decline in the trade deficit in the coming years.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

While the global digital transformation market size is expected to grow from USD 469.8 billion in 2020 to USD 1009.8 billion by 2025, at a CAGR of 16.5%, India's digital transformation market is expected to reach \$710.0 billion by 2024,

registering a CAGR of 74.7%.³ Combining digital transformation with AI and machine learning can produce the best outcomes and accelerate the transformation of key industries like manufacturing, BFSI, healthcare, MSME, and agriculture.

The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), Government of India launched the 'Digital India' program with the vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge-based economy by ensuring digital access, digital inclusion, digital empowerment, and bridging the digital divide. This campaign aims at improving online infrastructure, increasing access to the Internet, or empowering the country to use technology digitally.

To an industry that has largely accepted the status quo regarding their dependence on imports from nations like China, Taiwan, Korea, and other countries, PM Modi's call to make India "Self-Reliant" or "Atmanirbhar" is a clarion call for action. Our entire supply chain was crippled and disrupted during the COVID-19 lockdowns due to the enormous reliance. Covid-19 pandemic has rapidly changed digital transformation, it reshaped both "what" and "how" of companies.

TECHNOLOGICAL UPGRADATION

The revolutionary upgradation of technology in India has led to the holistic development and approach to unify, synergize, and converge to adapt to modern technology & enhance competitiveness in the global market. India has always been dynamic, progressive, and adaptive and this is true even in the context of technological innovations, advancements, and development in the outer world.

³ Nasscom

“Once a new technology rolls over you, if you're not part of the steamroller, you're part of the road.”

- Stewart Brand, Writer

The fourth industrial revolution is currently happening in the globe. New technologies are altering how various sectors of the economy function. Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence are central to IR 4.0, which will produce smart factories, in the middle of all of this.

India needs to do a lot of catching up as it is on the verge of a full digital transformation. Make in India, Digital India, and Startup India are just a few of the government's initiatives that could help India become an industrial and technological powerhouse.⁴IR 4.0 technologies must also clear the Atmanirbharta

⁴ Khanna Sandeep, June 2020, “ India needs ubiquitous iot connectivity to be truly atmanirbhar” <https://www.thebridgechronicle.com/opinion/india-needs-ubiquitous-iot-connectivity-be-truly-atmanirbhar-52133>

test established by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in order to prevent India from turning into a depository for antiquated technology.

Making India "AtmaNirbhar" is an enormous opportunity and challenge for the industry at the same time. Hardware, cloud stacks, mobile apps, data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI) are the essential building blocks of any Internet of Things product or solution.

Every Internet of Things (IoT) system needs a connectivity module, such as WiFi, BLE, LoRa, UWB, GSM, etc. Sadly, the majority of these are still imported. The good news is that to meet the rising demand for IoT, connectivity modules can be manufactured locally. The difficulty India encounters is the lack of local alternatives for producing semiconductors and other similar electronic components. Campaigns to ban Chinese goods, therefore, seem more paradoxical than practical. Only things that have an option are eligible for a boycott. As per Indian Electronics & Semiconductor Association (IESA), the Indian semiconductor industry is growing at 10.1% annually, is set to be worth \$ 32.35 billion by 2025 which establishes the demand.

For the cloud infrastructure portion, the majority of Indian IoT companies depend on Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform, or Microsoft Azure. These services provide a variety of customized features that simplify the work of an IoT developer in addition to affordable pricing and simple onboarding.⁵

Additionally, due to the dominance of Amazon Alexa and Google Home in the market for voice assistants, IoT developers naturally create a bias toward their

⁴ October 2020, "Atmanirbhar Bharat and Industry 4.0" <https://www.industrialautomationindia.in/articleitm/10852/Atmanirbhar-Bharat-and-Industry-4.0/articles>

parent companies. Like the Chinese government, the legislation should encourage and support the use of domestic cloud providers, but not to the point where it forbids other foreign players. To counter this, Indian businesses should invest a portion of their earnings in R&D activities to keep up with the competition.

If we can create a local manufacturing ecosystem that is very comparable to China and Taiwan and get the Indian industry's commitment to buying locally-made connectivity modules and, very soon we will conquer the global market. Once more, we would require assistance from the Indian government to create the appropriate framework, impose taxes on such imported components, and direct funding to businesses that execute ventures.

The advent of AI has been appropriately referred to as the fourth industrial revolution. Despite the fact that its creation and implementation demonstrate the promise of an independent India, promises are not an end in themselves. They must be carried out. In order for India to advance in becoming atmanirbhar, the pursuit of AI-driven technology must take place through the establishment of indigenous principles, moral and responsible benchmarks, and governance frameworks.

AI has the potential to add 1 trillion to India's economy and to boost India's annual growth rate by 1.3 percentage points by 2035. Fostering AI in the academia-industry can boost its research & application at the national level. It will push technology frontiers through the creation of new knowledge and in developing applications. Present Use cases of AI in India are in Smart Mobility and Transportation, Agriculture, Education, Healthcare, Smart Cities, and Infrastructure.

By meeting the quickly rising demand of the urbanized population and offering them a better quality of life, better traffic control to reduce congestion, and enhanced security through improved crowd management, AI can help transform

smart cities into intelligent cities. By utilizing image-recognition software, drone technology, and machine learning, AI in Farmer Portal enables farmers to earn more money by monitoring crops, predicting yields, encouraging precision farming, stabilizing yields, analyzing soil quality, and forecasting advisories for weather, sowing, pest control, and input control.

Another area where AI can be applied to monitor and analyze the issue of tax evasion, as well as to improve E-Governance and lessen the burden of compliance, is the Goods and Services Tax Network (GSTN).⁶The Government of India (GOI) has even initiated Project Insight, which uses machine learning to monitor frauds and illicit funds.

AI in BFSI is helping organizations to improve their operations and better serve their customers and is transforming the sector at global level. The market for AI in the BFSI sector was worth over USD 15 billion in 2021, and it is expected to expand at a rate of over 35% CAGR from 2022 to 2028.⁷ In India, the BFSI sector is gradually opening up to adopt innovative solutions to transform the banking system with initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, UPI, and the BharatNet mission, and AI can play a crucial role by adopting algorithms in Investments to increase portfolio returns and reduce risks, both for institutional and retail investors, by delivering personalized financial management advice and alerts to customers, by providing

⁶ Kumar Gandharv, August 2022, “AI can drive the future of Data-driven Bfsi sector” <https://indiaai.gov.in/article/ai-can-drive-the-future-of-the-data-driven-bfsi-sector>

⁷ September 2021, “ AI in India’s digital transformation” <https://community.nasscom.in/communities/digital-transformation/ai-indias-digital-transformation#:~:text=AI%20can%20help%20convert%20Smart,security%20using%20improved%20crowd%20management>.

smart transaction analysis programs and tools to detect fraud and money-laundering transactions and so.

AI is a core element of the Industry 4.0 revolution and use cases are spread across different areas, one of the industries using AI and machine learning most quickly is the telecom sector. It uses these technologies to increase network reliability, improve customer experiences, and even anticipate maintenance needs.

CONCLUSION

If India aspires to be a Self-Reliant (Aatmanirbhar)-a technology leader in letter, spirit, and action in the years to come, the nation has to work more toward propagation, advancements, and innovations. In today's era of rapid globalization, which is the need of the hour, greater adoption of technological developments will enable more entrepreneurs from India who can build products for a global user base.

By improvising on the tech, development, marketing, building communities, and providing opportunities for artists to present their work through digital means more jobs can be created. "India's technology services industry can achieve \$300-350 billion in annual revenue by 2025 if it can exploit the fast-emerging business potential in cloud, artificial intelligence (AI), cybersecurity, and other emerging technologies", according to a report by industry body Nasscom and global consulting firm McKinsey. With a significant portion of work coming from other countries and the placement of Indian specialists around the world, the future belongs to India.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Governments at the national and state (or local) levels must set up suitable venues for researchers and academics to engage in such research and freely and candidly discuss their findings if they are to truly put their own mark on domestic AI projects.
- With the increase in the digital infrastructure of the country, we have already seen the power that digitization yields in changing the face of a company, industry, or country. Spreading Digital awareness and empowering people with knowledge rather than digitizing everything along with relentless marketing of government schemes in rural and urban areas alike will help the scheme gain momentum, market share, and users.
- Training and events where we make professionals and graduates job-ready in the field of emerging technologies like AI, Data, Cloud, Robotics, and Metaverse, are the first steps to making India ready for the growing tech space.

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PARTICULARS

Ms. Nalini Shanker

Birla Institute of Management, Technology, Greater
Noida.

9917897656

Nalini.shanker23@bimtech.ac.in

Ms. Shambhavi Agarwal

Khandelwal College of Management, Science and
Technology, Bareilly (Affiliated to AKTU Lucknow)

6396647810

shambhaviagarwal.62@gmail.com

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